

INTERNATIONAL ASSOCIATION
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**FUTURE &
TRENDS IN
DISTANCE &
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EDUCATION**

**Proceedings of International Conference
held on May 18 & 19, 2021**

FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT IN E-COMMERCE

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Abstract

The Industrial Policy and Promotion Department recently invited feedback on the e-commerce FDI allowance and indicated that the Government intends to open this section. The new Indian policy does not encourage foreign investment in online sales to customers. There are no limitations on FDI in e-commerce transfers of products between company and business (B2B). Therefore, it considers going beyond B2C products retail into other transactions, such as consumer-to-government transactions (C2B), business-to-government transactions (B2Gs), and consumer-to-business transactions (C2Bs). This paper looks at the advantages of FDI in e-commerce. The paper is woven as a conceptual paper which can be used to address some of the big e-commerce problem facing FDI.

Keywords: Electronic-commerce, FDI, Foreign direct investment, e-commerce

1. INTRODUCTION

Electronic commerce might no longer be the disruptive mouthpiece in the late 1990s, however, when it matures; we are raising several questions regarding the improved customer reaction to e-commerce. According to the latest study by the Affiliated Chambers of Commerce and Industry, ASSOCHAM, the Indian e-commerce sector expanded 88 percent and amounted to \$16 billion in 2013. Increased internet access and more payment channels were added in 2013 to the e-commerce sector. The rapidly growing e-commerce industry in India is expected to be Rs. 50,000 crores. ASSOCHAM estimated that the Indian e-commerce industry, led by growing online shopping, reaches \$56 billion by 2023. This amounted to 2.5 billion dollars in 2009, to 8.5 billion dollars in 2012, and 88 percent to 16 billion dollars in 2013.

In India, the interest of global retailers to grow is coming at a time when local start-ups like Flipkart Internet Pvt. Ltd. and Snapdeal.com are launching into the competitive online retail gaming sector with a wide variety of goods offered by these retailers with reduced rates and quick payment methods, which have made them massive success in India, particularly with young consumers. The US-based Amazon and E-bay e-commerce firms operate in India using the marketplace model, and these companies pressure the Indian government to further open up the e-commerce industry to directly offer their goods to customers.

1.1 E-COMMERCE FDI IN INDIA, REGULATION

The current policy in India does not permit foreign investment in consumer online transactions, i.e. the current policies do not enable FDI in e-commerce business-to-consumer (B2C) operations, while 100 percent FDI in e-commerce business-to-business (B2B) and marketplace models are permitted, under which the e-retailer is not offered directly to customers. US-based Amazon and e-bay e-commerce firms work across a marketplace model in India.

2. PROBLEMS ON E-COMMERCE OF FDI ISSUE

The problem of Foreign Direct investment in online retailers is now widespread in the e-commerce market, with on the one hand international multinational companies such as Amazon favoring 100% FDI in this field and, on the other, major Indian players who are trying only partial opening-ups. The question of contention is:

- Whether the 100% FDI in e-commerce should be authorized.
- Or for non-strategic investors alone.
- If offline stores should be permitted by e-commerce to circumvent retail standards.
- If the local source should be restricted.
- If B2C e-commerce allows FDI
- Can it be available to any or only non-food items?

3. BOILING POINT OF FDI

Alongside the expectation of that FDI will do wonders for this field of e-commerce with lower constraints, other people have voiced their intense concern about it? Let us look at certain of these concerns:

- An aspect of extinction: One of the principal concerns of allowing FDI in e-commerce would severely undermine the short-term trade in bricks and mortar shops. Small shopkeepers are not highly trained and cannot cope with a healthy e-commerce business. The huge presence of e-commerce firms can reach far-reaching regions. Relocation of small shops is a huge problem.
- Geographical restrictions: Geographical restrictions on e-commerce, as applicable in the FDI MBRT Regulation, are also relevant (Multi-Brand Retail Trading). Following the MBRT scheme, States have been allowed to decide on the notification of towns and cities with populations above 10 lakhs following the 2011 census.
- Local Sourcing: At present, e-commerce companies like Amazon operate on an inventory-based model that could negatively influence SMEs and therefore emerge as in the case of multi-brand FDI the issue of local sourcing.

- Unemployment: The other serious problem of the small-time companies and Kirana businesses becoming the country's leading source of jobs and opening the e-commerce (B2C) to customers on an inventory-based model is likely to have a serious effect, which leads to large-scale unemployment. Taxation is, along with FDI, a crucial factor for the market model, business plan, and future development of e-retailers. The lack of physical limits and the intangible existence of transactions generate many income taxes and indirect tax problems at any point in the supply chain.
- Domain administration: The organization that maintains and manages the server is probably separate from the e-commerce agency hosting the website. e) Server management: There may be taxation problems if the server is situated outside India and is rented and run by an e-commerce company.
- Advertising and promotion: e-commerce firms provide different rewards for consumers such as credit points, cashback, cash rollover, rebuy one free discounts, combo pack discounts, and so forth. The value of indirect tax goods and services is generally dependent on earned considerations and could subject e-commerce firms to higher taxation, interest, and penalties.
- Processing of orders: if the e-commerce firms provide customer-based goods, they may proceed to a pre-determined sell which could be regarded as an interstate/CST trade contributing to the loss of tax credits.
- Purchase and maintenance of stocks: e-commerce firms participate in practices such as naming, repackaging, marking, re-affixing, gift wrapping, etc., for delivery to consumers goods. Based on the operation and the value-added of the finished product, it may classify as a 'deemed manufacturing,' charged for excise duties, under the Central Excise Law.
- Shipping and delivery: the supply chain of e-commerce firms is typically thin and therefore drop distribution is used whereby the e-commerce business provides the goods to its consumers directly. The seller, the e-commerce firm, and the buyer may be in separate countries and the tax position could change depending on the transaction. In addition, the registration and enforcement management in the respective States will provide the e-commerce business with major hurdles.
- Invoicing and collection: the USP is the prompt supply of goods to e-commerce firms. Transactions between the seller, e-commerce firms, and the buyer may be so arranged that the problem of the invoice, that is the ownership transfer record, would take place at a later date. The period for invoicing and the transaction time and location of possession are generally determined by the state VAT/CST law; the corporation will be exposed to the possibility of taxation, interests, and sanctions while deviating from the conformity and ownership aspects.

4. FDI advances in E-COMMERCE

The Internet has simplified our lives in more than one way and has even affected our everyday existence. India has 137 million internet users with 11 percent penetration. 71% of customer e-commerce transactions apply to travel. By 2020, the anticipated contribution of e-commerce to GDP will be around 4%. If we look at how we like to purchase products and services digitally relative to purchasing from a typical supermarket, the Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion (DIPP) article said that foreign direct investment (FDI) in business-to-market segments will also increase customer support.

- Growing infrastructural growth: expanded capital would lead to the development of supply, storage, and warehousing chain.
- The impulse to the manufacturing sector: retail sector development would have a cascading impact in the manufacturing industry that will lead positively to overall economic growth and employment creation.
- Effective supply chain management: would reduce the need for intermediaries, and reduces transaction costs, overheads, and product and labor costs.
- Adopting the best management standards globally: would improve the culture of work and customer experience.
- Expanded outreach: will offer buyers/sellers greater access; will enable MSMEs and craftsmen to meet their clients far outside their immediate location, locally and abroad.
- Traceability and transparency: would not only enhance knowledge and data compliance for customers but also improve compliance with the regulatory system.
- Reduced costs: Companies profit from promotion and distribution, transport, products, and supplies
- Customer support improvement: providing consumers with more efficient order collection and after-sales operation and competitive pricing
- Positive spillover impact: The growing e-commerce sector has already been said to have a positive spillover effect on relevant industries like logistics, internet advertisement, the media as well as IT/ITES. E-commerce now accounts for 15-20 percent of some of the major logistics firms' overall sales.
- Availability of FDIs in this field, rather than international actors such as Amazon and eBay, can help established local enterprises, who need more capital to expand their businesses on an increasingly rising market. It could also contribute to a stronger work atmosphere, knowledge, and better customer support by supplying consumers with more sensitive orders and post-sales resources coupled with reasonable pricing.

5. CONCLUSION

In all, electronic shopping and online retail in India constitutes a small fraction of all revenues but would expand to a substantial degree because of a lot of factors including growing availability incomes, rapid urbanization, increased usage, and penetration of technology such as the Internet and mobile devices, rising young demographics as well as rising costs of operating offline shops throughout the world. U.S. e-commerce giants Amazon and E-bay are driving the Indian government to further open up the e-commerce market so that it can directly offer the goods to customers. The draught policies for foreign direct investment in e-commerce have been opposed by the merchants but the views held by global and domestic e-commerce firms are mixed. India's e-commerce vendor association is also divided on the FDI issue. In e-commerce, FDI would fuel the growth of infrastructure and stimulate demand, but may also trigger major job losses. Finally, before allowing FDI into e-commerce, the Government remains awaiting the views of all stakeholders and everything depends on which political party would be in the core of government.

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Publication Div:
Bestow Edutrex International LLP
S2, 303, Sundar Nagar, Malad W,
Mumbai 64
email: info@bestowedutrex.co.in

RS : 350/-